

Style for IRRN Contributors

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Germplasm conservation

Observations on local rice germplasm in Liberia

S. S. Vjrmami, visiting scientist, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute (formerly rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture [IITA], Central Agricultural Experiment Station [CAES], Suakoko, Bong County, Republic of Liberia)

In 1977, 469 local rice varieties (mostly dryland), including 60 varieties of the African cultigen *Oryza glaberrima*, were collected by the Ministry of Agriculture, in collaboration with the Genetic Resources Unit of the IITA. These rices were maintained and evaluated at the CAES, Suakoko, in 1978–79.

The following observations were made on the materials:

1. Various agronomic characteristics that can be used in breeding programs such as height, tillering, growth duration, photoperiod sensitivity, and grain size and shape had high genetic variability. In the 1978 wet season, 209 single plants were selected for breeding in the progeny of those materials evaluated under dryland conditions.

2. The local varieties showed genetic variability. Variants and off-type plants were found among progeny of 74% of the single-panicle rows and 34% of the bulk rows. The variants included: dwarf to semidwarf plants among tall; photoperiod-insensitive (flowering) among photoperiod-sensitive (non-flowering) during the dry season under wetland conditions; purple culm bases among green culm bases; and typical to intermediate *glaberrima* types among *O. sativa*, and vice versa. These observations indicate that outcrossing as well as mechanical mixtures may occur in farmers' varietal populations. The presence of intermediate types of *O. sativa*-*O. glaberrima* indicates that *O. glaberrima* may provide such mechanisms.

Some dryland rice farmers reported that *O. glaberrima* plants continued to occur in their rice fields, despite attempts to rogue them.

Further studies are required to clearly identify the nature of genetic segregation and the role of *O. glaberrima* in providing an outcrossing mechanism in local dryland rice varieties. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal resistance to rice diseases and insects in Liberia

S. S. Vjrmami, visiting scientist, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute (formerly rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture [IITA], Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Bong County, Liberia)

Liberia is in the tropical forest zone of high rainfall in West Africa and the country's ecological conditions are favorable for many rice diseases and insects. In conditions of subsistence

farming (shifting cultivation), the pests' severity is not usually apparent, but under permanent or intensive rice farming, the pests become obvious.

Rice diseases identified in Liberia include blast *Pyricularia oryzae*, leaf scald *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, brown spot *Helminthosporium oryzae*, sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, sheath blight *Corticium sasakii*, sheath blotch *Pyrenochaeta oryzae*, glume discoloration (caused by various fungi), false smut *Ustilagoidea virens*, udbatta *Ephelis oryzae*, and pale yellow mottle virus. The most serious are blast, leaf scald,